

In Depth Battery Aging Analysis: A Key to Sustainable Energy Storage in Microgrids

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Abstract—The increasing use of renewable energy makes balancing generation and demand in power systems more challenging, which has led to a growing focus on battery technologies and energy storage solutions. These systems are essential for the effective integration of renewable energy into sustainable power networks. However, most experimental studies of lithium-ion batteries are limited to deep charge and discharge cycles, which do not fully represent how batteries operate in stationary applications. In these applications, batteries experience not only the main charge and discharge processes but also additional stress from current fluctuations due to the variable nature of renewable energy. These smaller cycles, known as micro-cycles, have a depth of discharge less than 2% and occur alongside the primary charge and discharge processes. This paper presents the results of an experimental study focused on battery aging, considering micro-cycles that emulate real-world conditions for batteries in microgrid storage systems. It demonstrates that the degradation in storage systems occurs differently compared to deep charge and discharge cycles. It provides a detailed analysis of the degradation processes occurring in microgrid batteries using EIS diagnostics and post-mortem analysis and demonstrates the applicability of the findings for renewable energy systems.

Index Terms—battery degradation, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, energy storage, lithium-ion battery, microgrid, renewable energy

I. INTRODUCTION

ELECTRIFICATION of the automotive transport sector and the transition to sustainable energy are two of the most significant challenges facing modern society [1]. One approach to address these challenges is by microgrids, which provide a platform for integrating renewable distributed generation. By incorporating energy storage systems and flexible loads, microgrids create a localized, small-scale power

system that offers numerous advantages, such as enhanced operational flexibility, improved system reliability, and cost-efficient operation [2]. As the demand for integrating higher levels of renewable energy grows and the need to reduce the costs of meeting peak demand intensifies, energy storage technologies have gained increasing attention. These systems enable the shifting of energy from peak-demand periods to off-peak times or the storage of excess renewable energy for later use, supplying it back to the grid when needed. Additionally, their fast-ramping capabilities make energy storage a highly competitive resource for addressing the variability and uncertainty that come with renewable energy generation [3].

For the energy storage purposes, lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries are used due to their high energy density and long cycle life [4]. While the technology of power converters and other electrical equipment of the battery energy storages has been improved by decades and it is now well-established technology, the electrochemical reactions taking place in Li-ion batteries are still not a fully explored area [5].

Moreover, although the cost of battery storage is one of the key parameters affecting the overall cost of a microgrid [6], batteries are often treated merely as a black box, and the impact of operating conditions on their lifespan is not given sufficient attention during the design of sustainable energy systems [2], [3], [7], [8], [9], [10].

For instance, Wang et al., in their 2020 work proposing a new approach to energy storage management [2], estimate battery degradation using a formula from 1997 that was empirically derived for NiCd batteries. This model, however, is not applicable to the Li-ion batteries that are commonly used in modern energy storage systems. Similarly, Bandyopadhyay et al. [10], in their study on the optimal sizing of photovoltaic-battery microgrid systems, used an empirical battery degradation model originally validated for electric vehicles, which only considered deep charge and discharge cycles. The charging and discharging profile of a battery storage system integrated into a microgrid, however, involves only a negligible number of full deep cycles [11]. This prompts the question of whether these simplifications are appropriate for ensuring the sustainable and cost-effective operation of storage systems.

Li et al. [3] in their work estimate the economic savings of an energy system with battery storage, with the lifespan of the system determined solely based on achievable Equivalent Full Cycles (EFC) and the manufacturer's datasheet.

Even though it is known that the number of cycles has a major influence on a battery's lifetime [12], it also depends on other factors, such as operating temperature and voltage and

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current limit values [13]. For these reasons, many laboratory studies have been carried out to investigate the impact of these parameters on lifespan of energy storages by charging and discharging batteries under specific conditions [14], [15], [16], [17]. Thanks to these studies, it is well accepted that factors such as charge throughput or temperature lead to battery aging.

However, in the real operation of stationary energy storage systems, short-term reverse current throughput occurs [18]. These fluctuations during charging or discharging that do not exceed 2% of State of Charge (SOC) can be defined as micro-cycles. Based on research by Li et al. [19] who present, that battery lifetime decreases with increasing current throughput, micro-cycles could be expected to accelerate the State of Health (SOH) reduction during the use of a battery.

On the other hand, Vazini et al. [20] present the positive effect of short pulses, where with sinusoidal ripple current charging, the battery reached an 80% SOC 10% faster than with conventional Constant Current – Constant Voltage (CC-CV) charging. Additionally, the temperature during the sinusoidal charging process was approximately 0.5 °C lower. Furthermore, ripple charging can reduce ohmic losses by 52% compared to CC-CV charging [21].

From the perspective of changes in electrochemical reactions and types of degradation processes, this topic is addressed by Ming Wang et al. [22], who present the effect of current pulses on Solid Electrolyte Interface (SEI) formation. They suggest that the charging type also affects the composition and structure of the SEI layer, which could directly impact the overall battery lifespan. For diagnosing these internal structural changes, one can use non-destructive methods such as Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) [23] or post-mortem analysis, and observe changes in the microstructures of the individual electrodes using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) [24].

These aspects demonstrate that understanding the subtle interplay between micro-cycling and electrochemical processes in Li-ion batteries is essential for enhancing their reliability, safety, and overall performance in energy storage.

For these reasons, the previous work of A. Soto et al. [4], which published capacity measurements indicating that micro-cycles have a positive effect on the lifetime of Li-ion batteries, was followed by EIS analysis to gain a deeper understanding of the reasons for different capacity fade in cells aged with and without micro-cycles [1]. The main contribution was the inference of reasons for variability in capacity fade, which were mainly attributed to differing growth of the SEI layer. Intrinsically, one of the future directions was to conduct a post-mortem analysis to confirm the conclusions of our work.

This work is an extension of the conference paper [1] and incorporates post-mortem analysis to address the need for understanding the lifespan of batteries and the dependency of degradation processes on micro-cycling phenomena comprehensively from multiple perspectives including capacity testing, EIS diagnostics and post-mortem analysis.

The main contribution of this work is the EIS analysis of the cells, which is linked with post-mortem analysis of the anode and cathode of the cell, which, based on Laser Scanning Microscopy. Results demonstrate that micro-cycles lead to up to four times slower growth of the SEI layer, thereby slowing

down battery degradation and presents the potential applicability of these conclusions in the design and operation of energy storages.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Battery Usage Profiles in Renewable Energy Applications

To properly study the degradation processes in batteries used within microgrids, it is essential to understand the real-world loading profiles that the battery storage system experiences during operation. The aging experiments presented in this paper are designed to reflect typical battery operation profiles in renewable energy systems.

The real operation of a 3.3 kWh Li-ion battery installed in a self-consumption system in northern Spain (42°48'00.6"N 1°38'04.4"W) was monitored over a 52-week period, and the data collected were subsequently analyzed using the Rain flow algorithm to serve as input for the aging experiments [11]. The number of cycles per Depth of Discharge (DOD) obtained for a self-consumption installation during 52 weeks of operation are illustrated in Fig. 1. Given the substantial number of micro-cycles, it is crucial to properly assess their impact on the aging of Li-ion batteries. Consequently, a test matrix was developed, incorporating the effect of the most recurrent micro-cycles.

B. Experimental Aging of Li-ion Batteries with Micro-cycles

The tested batteries in this work were LG 18650 Li-ion cells with a nominal capacity of 3 Ah. According to the manufacturer's information, each cell consists of a graphite + SiO₂ anode and H-NMC cathode. The nominal cell voltage of the selected cell is 3.6 V, and the operating voltage range is from 2.5 V to 4.2 V.

All experiments were performed in the Laboratory for Energy Storage and Microgrids at the Public University of Navarra in an Ineltec -30/300 thermal chamber at a controlled temperature of 20 °C ± 0.5 °C. A Neware BTS4016-5V battery tester was used for testing. The data was obtained via four-

Fig. 1. Number of cycles per DOD obtained for a self-consumption installation during 52 weeks of operation [1].

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TABLE I
MICRO-CYCLE TEST MATRIX

	Number of tested cells	Depth of micro-cycle
Continuous deep charge – discharge cycles with a current of 3 A (1C)	2	0%
Deep charge – discharge with superimposed micro-cycles	2	0.5%
Deep charge – discharge with superimposed micro-cycles	2	1%
Deep charge – discharge with superimposed micro-cycles	2	2%

terminal sensing method and the cell temperature was constantly monitored.

A total of eight cells in four different scenarios were used for the experiment. Three scenarios included deep cycles superimposed with micro-cycling of different DODs. One scenario consisted only of deep cycles and it was used as a baseline. The test matrix is shown in Table I.

Fig. 2 shows the aging profiles, in which the micro-cycles with DOD of 0.5% (red), 1% (blue) and 2% (green) are superimposed to a deep cycle. The DOD of the deep cycles shown in the figure is 80% (in terms of nominal capacity), which is limited by the reaching of the maximum cell voltage during the last part of the charge. Given that the experiments are done at the same current, the cycle with no micro-cycles (grey) is done faster than those with micro-cycles. The time between micro-cycles is adjusted, so that the batteries with micro-cycles of 0.5%, 1% and 2% complete a full cycle at the same time. In this work, the SOH is defined in Eq. (1), and the end of life (EOL) criteria is set as $SOH < 70\%$.

$$SOH = 100 \cdot \frac{C}{C_i}, \quad (1)$$

being C the current charge capacity and C_i the initial capacity.

C. Reference performance tests

°Reference Performance Tests (RPTs) are periodically performed each 20 cycles to monitor the cells' degradation. To minimize their influence on the aging process, the following RPT procedure is applied:

1. Discharge the cell to its minimum voltage at a current of 1 A (C/3).

Fig. 2. Aging profiles of the cells.

2. Charge the cell to its maximum voltage at 1 A (C/3), followed by a constant-voltage stage until the current drops to 0.12 A (C/25).
3. Discharge the cell again at 1 A (C/3) to the minimum voltage.
4. Charge the cell using galvanostatic pulses with increments of $\Delta SOC = 20\%$, at a current of 1 A.
5. Allow the cell to rest for 1 hour after each galvanostatic charge pulse.
6. Discharge the cell to SOC = 50% at a current of 1 A (C/3) and let it rest for 1 hour.
7. Perform an EIS.

D. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy Method

The EIS method was used in this work to provide a deeper analysis of battery cells' materials and mechanisms in a nondestructive manner. During EIS measurements, a small AC signal over a wide frequency range is applied to the battery, and the cell response is measured [23]. Different components and processes within a cell operate on different timescales. Therefore, they have different time constants and can be separated in the frequency domain using this method. The most significant advantage of EIS is its measurement time, which is much shorter related to, for example, capacity testing, and another significant advantage is its possibility to analyze separately the chemical processes inside the battery [12].

Fig. 3 illustrates the relationship between the different parts of EIS chart and the chemical processes within battery. This makes it possible to examine the different processes in parallel and to better determine what is happening inside battery under the different aging profiles.

As shown in Fig. 3, each part of the graph is linked to one of the chemical processes taking place inside the battery [25], [26]. More specifically, these processes can be quantified using an Equivalent Electrical Circuit (EEC), where each process is linked to an element of the EEC [27]. The selected EEC, based on work of Sihvo et al. [28], consists of serial resistance R_s , serial inductance L_s , and three components composed of constant phase element (CPE) and resistance R_x in parallel. CPE is defined as [29] :

$$Z_{CPE} = \frac{1}{Q(j\omega)^N}. \quad (2)$$

Here, j is the imaginary unit, Q is the pre-factor of the CPE, and

Fig. 3. Impedance plot of a NMC battery cell.

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N is its exponent. Q parameter describes the position in the Nyquist graph relative to the y-axis and is the generalized capacitance, the N parameter represents how much the semicircle is deformed from the ideal semicircle in terms of Nyquist plot. The meaning of each parameter is given in Table II.

Chosen equivalent electrical circuit is shown in Fig. 4. The fitting algorithm was created in Matlab software, using toolbox Zfit [30].

E. Post-mortem analysis

The post-mortem analysis was carried out at the Electrical Energy Storage Technology group laboratories, in TU Berlin. To do the post-mortem analysis, the cells were discharged to their end-of-discharge (EOD) voltage at a current of 0.1 C. Then, they were opened in a glovebox under an argon atmosphere (glovebox type MBRAUN UNILab pro, O_2 and H_2O concentration < 1 ppm). A Keyence VK-X200 series laser microscope, which was placed inside the same glovebox, was used to perform Laser Scanning Microscopy (LSM) of the samples extracted from the anodes and cathodes of the cells.

The Keyence VK-X200 microscope combines an optical image with a high-resolution laser image to provide a highly augmented image with high resolution, including a better visual result by means of the optical lens. This kind of image shows the evolution of the pore structure during the lifetime of the cells that undergo full cycles and allows its comparison with cells with a cycling profile that also includes micro-cycles. On the other hand, the LSM images provide an accurate measurement of the surface thickness, allowing the analysis of the SEI layer distribution, lithium plating, as well as dendrite formation.

Post-mortem analysis was performed over four cells. The first one was a pristine cell, in which the original characteristics of the electrodes after manufacturing can be observed. The second cell also was almost pristine, but it had undergone 20 full charge-discharge cycles that ensured the formation of a stable SEI layer [31]. The third cell had an SOH of 68%, which was reached with full charge-discharge cycles with 2%-DOD micro-cycles superimposed, as described in row 4 of Table 1. Finally, the fourth cell had a SOH of 65%, similar to cell 3, but reached this SOH by means of only full charge-discharge cycles, as described in row 1 of Table 1. This experimental design allows a comparative study of new cells, cells aged with micro-cycles, and cells aged without micro-cycles.

Fig. 4. EEC used for fitting measured EIS curves.

TABLE II
EEC PARAMETERS DESCRIPTION

EEC part	EEC parameter description – physical meaning
R_s	ohmic resistance of the cell
L_s	parasitic inductance and inductance of supply cables
$R_1 CPE_1$	parameters related to the impedance at frequencies of about 1 Hz - 100 Hz and to the processes taking place in the SEI layer
$R_2 CPE_2$	charge transfer of the electrochemical reaction
$R_3 CPE_3$	parameters related to diffusion in battery

III. RESULTS

A. Capacity Fade: Comparing Aging with and without Micro-cycles

As demonstrated in the work of A. Soto et al. [4], the aging processes with and without micro-cycles exhibit differing rates of degradation, as illustrated in the Fig. 5. Analyzing the number of achievable EFCs in terms of Ah throughput in the case with micro-cycles reveals that it is possible to attain approximately one-third more equivalent full cycles compared to the scenario without micro-cycles, before the battery reaches its end of life, defined as 70% of its nominal capacity.

Based on these results, the experimental data were subjected to a more detailed analysis using EIS and microscopic images.

B. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy Diagnostics

The main difference between cells subjected to micro-cycles and cells without micro-cycles are found in parameters R_1 and Q_1 , as shown in Fig. 6. Specifically, fourfold increase in R_1 resistance occurs 1000 EFCs earlier in batteries aged without micro-cycles, as shown in Fig. 6c, and a more significant deviation of the traces of Q_1 for cells without micro-cycles is observed in Fig. 6e.

The remaining impedance parameters show no significant

Fig. 5. Experimental measurement of SOH in 8 cells as a function of EFC.

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Fig. 6. EEC parameters evolution based on EFC: a) Series resistance; b) series inductance; c) resistance related to SEI layer, e) and f) parameters of CPE related to SEI layer; d) resistance related to charge transfer region; g) and h) parameters of CPE related to charge transfer region.

difference between the various cycling profiles. These two parameters (R_1 and Q_1) are attributed to the growth of the SEI layer built between the anode and the electrolyte [1]. Given that the remaining parameters are homogeneous among cells, no relevant difference is expected in the electric conductivity of the electrodes and ionic conductivity of the electrolyte, modelled by R_s , or the charge transfer phenomena occurring in both electrodes, represented by Q_2 , N_2 , and R_2 .

C. Post-mortem Analysis of Microscopic Images

The post-mortem study presented herein is designed to validate the above-mentioned conclusions extracted from the non-destructive EIS analysis. To do so, the cells described in Section II-F are disassembled, and optical and LSM images of different parts of the anode and cathode are compiled.

Anode analysis

Fig. 7 shows the LSM (left) and height map (right) images of the studied anodes. Fig. 7a shows a portion of the pristine cell anode. The optical microscope image shows a clear particle distribution of the anode, with particle diameters in the order of hundreds of nm. The SEI layer is thin, allowing a clear

differentiation of anode particles. The result of the LSM analysis shows a more accurate representation of the anode height. The surface of the pristine anode is quite even, with a maximum difference between the deepest and the highest point of around 30 μm . A comparison between the optical and LSM images shows that the darker areas of the optical result are the deepest regions of the anode particle structure. By contrast, the anode particles that are lighter in the optical image are the highest parts in the height map representation.

Fig. 7b shows the results of the cell that has undergone 20 full charge – discharge cycles. The SEI formation process can be considered finished. Optical and LSM images show very similar results to those described for the pristine cell. This similarity makes sense, given that the SEI layer is designed to be as thin and even as possible. The edges of individual particles are clearly distinguishable, indicating that only the necessary growth of the initial SEI layer has occurred to stabilize the anode, without hindering the free movement of ions.

In contrast, in Fig. 7c on the left, which shows the optical image of the anode from a cell subjected to micro-cycles, the individual anode particles are less distinguishable, with some almost merging into one. This is attributed to lithium plating, meaning lithium particles are depositing without participating in charging and discharging processes, leading to a decrease in capacity. However, the height map remains practically the same as in cells with 100% capacity. There is a small lighter area indicating a slightly more uneven anode surface, though it only represents a variation of a few tens of percent.

In Fig. 7d, which is the post-mortem analysis of the cell cycled without micro-cycles, notable differences are immediately apparent in both the optical image and LSM result. In the optical image, the edges of individual particles are entirely unrecognizable, as they merge in the darker areas of the image, which are lower, while only tall protrusions, appearing lighter, are visible on the surface. The analysis of the LSM height map confirms the conclusions from the optical images, showing that the anode height has increased by more than four times compared to the pristine cell. The surface inhomogeneity of the anode is also significantly greater, which could accelerate further uneven degradation processes and, in extreme cases, lead to separator puncture and internal short circuits [32].

In these images, it is very clear that degradation phenomena with and without micro-cycles have a distinctly different effect on the SEI layer. While degradation with full cycle cycling produces a highly irregular lithium plating on the electrode surface, degradation with micro-cycles results in a much more homogeneous SEI growth. This can be attributed to the inversed polarization of the anode caused by the micro-cycles, which promotes ion diffusion within the anode, thus reducing metallic lithium plating. The lithium plated when the cell is cycled without micro-cycles prevents lithium-ion intercalation in plated anode areas, thereby increasing the current density of the remaining regions, which in turn accelerates the degradation of these areas and, consequently, the cell as a whole.

Cathode analysis

The results obtained from optical microscopy and LSM height

Fig. 7. Optical image and LSM height map of anode.

map analysis of the cathode are shown in Fig. 8. Similar to the anode analysis, these images allow a comparative analysis of the cathode surface at various aging stages. The LSM images have the same scale as those of Fig. 7, while the height map vertical axis is 4 times smaller in Fig. 8, given the lower growth of the cathode surface during aging.

Fig. 8.a) shows the cathode of the pristine cell, where individual particles are already less distinguishable at first glance. This is, however, an expected condition and one of the main reasons why LSM images alone are typically insufficient for post-mortem analysis [33]. From the height map analysis, even cathode surface can be observed, with a few small protrusions likely resulting from imperfections in the manufacturing process.

Fig. 8 b) on the left, showing the cathode after the initial cycling (the first 20 cycles), presents a similar optical image to that of the pristine cell, which is unsurprising given the low cycle count. The LSM height map reveals a slightly lower average cathode height, which could be due to, for example, the loss of active material from the cathode. However, these height differences are relatively insignificant and could just as well be attributed to the inhomogeneity of the cathode.

The optical image in Fig. c) is similar to all previous analyses of the cathode, however, compared to the LSM height maps in Fig. 8.a) and Fig. 8.b), the cathode surface is significantly more uniform, which could indicate the formation of a cathode surface layer primarily due to electrolyte oxidation [33].

In Fig. 8.d), showing the optical image, a small fibrous

structure is notable, which could be associated with the phenomenon of transition metal dissolution. This process involves the dissolution of cathode metal, potentially leading to dendrite growth or migration to the anode, causing an increase in the SEI layer. This phenomenon may correspond to the small peaks observed in the height map image. Additionally, the non-homogeneous surface could result from impurities introduced during manufacturing or disassembly.

Cathode degradation phenomena are observed by a comparative analysis of the images shown in Fig. 8. The pristine cell, as well as the cell with 20 charge – discharge cycles have similar distribution of the cathode particles (optical image), and similar roughness, visualized by the height map. The cathode of the cell aged with full cycles and micro-cycles (Fig. 8c) has also an even distribution of the particles and surface, showing no significant sign of aging. Finally, the cathode of the cell cycled only with full cycles, shown in Fig. 8d, shows a similar particle distribution, but in the height map, a significant particle deposition is appreciated. This deposition is not attributed to cathode aging, given that the remaining parts of the cathode show no significant degradation sign.

IV. DISCUSSION

The post-mortem analysis results described earlier align with the findings from previous sections regarding the capacity and impedance evolution of the cells during aging. Firstly, the capacity analysis showed a faster degradation of the cells cycled without micro-cycles, compared to those cycled with micro-

Fig. 8. Optical image and LSM height map of cathode.

cycles. Secondly, the non-destructive impedance analysis points towards the anode SEI as the reason for the different degradation rate, given that the largest difference is found in parameters R_I and Q_I . Finally, the post-mortem analysis, that requires the destruction of the cells, shows the most significant difference of the material aging in the anode surface, which is the region where the SEI is built.

It is interesting to note that the micro-cycles of the experiments presented in this paper almost double the lifespan of the cells in terms of EFC. If the EOL criteria is set at 70% SOH, the lifetime of cells used without micro-cycles ranges between 1400 and 1900 EFC, as shown in Fig. 5. However, cells with superimposed micro-cycles last around 3500 EFC.

The differences in the profiles of EEC parameters extracted from EIS curves also correspond with this conclusion. The parameters R_I and Q_I show the most significant differences. While cells aged without micro-cycles exhibit a fourfold increase in R_I at approximately 1500 EFC, for cells aged with micro-cycles, this increase occurs around EFC 3000, which completely aligns with the differences observed in capacity fade. A similar phenomenon is observable in Q_I , where a tenfold increase in the Q_I parameter occurs at 1500 EFC for cells without micro-cycles, whereas for cells with micro-cycles, this increase does not occur until around 2700 EFC.

As described in Section II. E., the parameters R_I and Q_I

represent the growth of the SEI layer, which occurs on the anode. Therefore, when we compare the results of the EIS analysis with the post-mortem analysis of anodes, we reach the exact same conclusion: The SEI layer grows several times faster in cells aged without micro-cycles, as illustrated in height map Fig 7 d. and its comparison with the remaining analyzed cells in that figure.

The comparison of capacity fade, EIS curves, and post-mortem analysis clearly demonstrates that the difference in aging rates is primarily due to the varying growth rates of the SEI layer, which is one of the most significant degradation processes in Li-ion batteries.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a detailed study of degradation processes occurring in Li-ion batteries aged under conditions typical for sustainable microgrids - deep cycles with superimposed micro-cycles and compare them with conventional deep discharge and charge cycling, which is still the most widely used method for studying battery lifespan.

Our results indicate that batteries subjected to micro-cycles reach 70% SOH approximately 2,000 Equivalent Full Cycles later than those subjected to conventional deep discharge and charging, resulting in a twofold increase in operational lifespan in terms of EFC. Through EIS diagnostics, the SEI layer

growth, which includes lithium plating, is identified to be the main contributor to this different aging evolution. Subsequently, the post-mortem analysis supports the EIS results, given that the anode of a cell cycled with full charge – discharge cycles has a significant surface affection caused mainly by growth of SEI layer.

Based on the findings of our study, we conclude that micro-cycles significantly affect the degradation process of Li-ion batteries, effectively extending cell lifespan in terms of EFC. Furthermore, our research demonstrates, that post-mortem analysis is particularly advantageous for examining anode modifications and tracking SEI layer growth. While optical imaging is suitable for the rapid assessment of particle alterations, quantification of degradation processes necessitates the use of LSM height map analysis.

Our results also substantiate that the EEC parameters Q_I and R_I accurately represent anode changes, thereby confirming EIS as a precise, non-destructive diagnostic tool for monitoring SEI layer growth across the battery lifecycle.

All in all, if this detailed knowledge of degradation processes is considered in the design and dimensioning of battery storage systems for microgrids, it can be expected that algorithms utilizing this knowledge will be gentler on battery performance within the storage system.

Firstly, it can be used for the extension of the lifetime of a battery by superimposing micro-cycles in the charging profile. Moreover, it can be used for a more accurate estimation of battery lifetime, thereby improving the economic analysis of the energy storage system. Finally, this contribution can also be used for the improvement of battery materials and cell design.

Overall, the proposed approach can improve the accuracy of life expectancy estimates and reduce the expected costs for sustainable energy systems.

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